

Vapor – Liquid Equilibria at 715 mm/Hg in the Systems n-Butyl Bromide – Trichloroethylene and n-Butyl Bromide – Tetrachloroethylene

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Boiling temperatures were measured for the binary systems n-butyl bromide with trichloroethylene and tetrachloroethylene at 715 mm/Hg. The data were correlated by Wilson equation and the excess Gibbs energies at 25° were calculated.

THE present work forms part of a program of measurement of excess thermodynamic properties of non-electrolyte binary solutions. In this paper we present boiling temperature measurement and derived excess Gibbs energies for two binary systems of n-butyl bromide with chloroethylenes.

Experimental

A Swietoslawski ebullimeter¹ was used for the measurement of the boiling points of the mixtures. The condenser of the ebullimeter was connected through a ballast to a vacuum system to ensure the required pressure. The pressure was regulated by a valve at the required constant value which is then determined with a U-tube mercury monometer. The temperature of the boiling mixtures was measured with a precalibrated platinum resistance thermometer connected to a digital display with 0.1° resolution. Mixtures of known composition were prepared gravimetrically and introduced into the ebullimeter. When a steady state was reached, the temperature was read.

All the chemicals were purified by the reported methods². n-Butyl bromide (Fluka, AG 99%, GC pure) was used as such. Trichloroethylene (veb) and tetrachloroethylene (veb) were fractionally distilled. All the compounds were dried over activated molecular sieves. The purity of the samples was checked by measuring density, refractive index and boiling point. Density was measured with a standard bicapillary pycnometer which gave an accuracy of 5 parts in 10⁵. Refractive index was determined with a Abbe's refractometer which gave an accuracy of ±0.0002. The measured values are in good agreement with the literature values^{3,4}.

Results and Discussion

For the two binary systems the boiling point curves were determined at 715 mm/Hg. The experimental data are reported in Table 1 and represented in Figs. 1 and 2.

The vapor-phase compositions and excess Gibbs free energies can be calculated if a model is assumed for the activity coefficients in the liquid phase. The empirical parameters of the model can then be calculated from the experimental data by minimising the objective function,

$$F = \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{P_{\text{exptl}} - P_{\text{calcd}}}{P_{\text{exptl}}} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

where, P_{exptl} and P_{calcd} are the experimental and calculated values of the total boiling pressures at

Fig. 1. 1-Bromobutane + 1,1,1-trichloroethylene at 715 mm/Hg: (—) liquid and (---) vapour.

Fig. 2. 1-Bromobutane + 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethylene at 715 mm/Hg: (-) liquid and (- -) vapour

TABLE 1—MOLE FRACTION (X_1) OF n-BUTYLBROMIDE AND BOILING TEMPERATURES OF MIXTURES OF n-BUTYLBROMIDE WITH CHLOROETHYLENES

X_1	T °C	X_1	T °C
n-Butylbromide-trichloroethylene		n-Butylbromide-tetrachloroethylene	
0.1041	88.0	0.0969	114.6
0.2046	88.2	0.2012	113.0
0.3007	90.4	0.3073	109.5
0.3908	91.6	0.4008	107.4
0.4992	93.1	0.4963	105.7
0.6044	94.3	0.6049	103.9
0.7012	94.6	0.7081	103.3
0.7994	96.8	0.7953	101.9
0.8970	98.3	0.8932	100.5

the i -th run for a mixture at composition x and temperature t and N is the number of experimental data. The calculation of the boiling pressure at each point was made by solving equation (2),

$$P_{\text{calcd}} = \frac{\gamma_1(x,t) X f_{1,L}^{\circ}(t,P)}{\hat{\phi}_1(Y,P,t)} + \frac{\gamma_2(x,t) (1-x) f_{2,L}^{\circ}(t,P)}{\hat{\phi}_2(Y,P,t)} \quad (2)$$

where, γ_1 and γ_2 are the activity coefficients given by the liquid-phase model chosen, $f_{i,L}^{\circ}$ is the standard-state fugacity of component i at temperature t and pressure P and $\hat{\phi}_i$ is the fugacity coefficient for component i in the vapor mixture. For normal liquids,

the standard-state fugacity $f_{i,L}^{\circ}$ at temperature t and pressure P is given by,

$$f_{i,L}^{\circ} = P_{s,i}(t) \phi_{s,i}(t) \exp \left[\gamma_{1,L} \left(\frac{P - P_{s,i}}{RT} \right) \right] \quad (3)$$

where, $P_{s,i}$ is the vapor pressure of component i at temperature t , $\phi_{s,i}$ is the fugacity coefficient of pure component i at saturation condition, and $V_{1,L}$ is the liquid molar volume of component i which is estimated by the modified Rackett equation⁵. The vapor pressure of pure components can be calculated by means of Antoine's equation. The Antoine constants are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ANTOINE CONSTANTS OF PURE COMPONENTS

Compd.	A	B	C
n-Butyl bromide	6 922 54	1 298 61	219 720
Trichloroethylene	7 028 06	1 315 10	230 000
Tetrachloroethylene	7 020 02	1 415 49	221 000

The fugacity coefficients $\hat{\phi}_i$ and $\phi_{s,i}$ were calculated by means of the virial equation of state,

$$\ln \phi_{s,i} = B_1 P_{s,i} \quad (4)$$

$$\ln \hat{\phi}_i = (P/RT) [B_1 + (1 - Y_i)^2 \delta_{12}] \quad (5)$$

$$\text{with } \delta_{12} = 2B_{12} - B_1 - B_2 \quad (6)$$

where B_1 and B_2 are the second virial coefficients of components 1 and 2, respectively, and B_{12} is the cross virial coefficient. The second virial coefficients were calculated by Tsonopoulos's correlation. For calculating the cross virial coefficient (B_{12}) the interaction parameter (K_{12}) is taken as 0.12, which was suggested by Tsonopoulos⁶ for similar systems. The effect of uncertainty in this value as Y values is negligible and is less than 0.2% even when K_{12} was taken as zero^{7,8}.

The model chosen to describe the activity coefficients in the liquid phase is the Wilson model⁹,

$$\ln \gamma_1 = -\ln (X_1 + \Delta_{12} X_2) + X_2 \left(\frac{\Delta_{12}}{X_1 + \Delta_{12} X_2} + \frac{\Delta_{21}}{X_2 + \Delta_{21} X_1} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$\ln \gamma_2 = -\ln (X_2 + \Delta_{21} X_1) + X_1 \left(\frac{\Delta_{21}}{X_2 + \Delta_{21} X_1} - \frac{\Delta_{12}}{X_1 + \Delta_{12} X_2} \right) \quad (8)$$

where,

$$\Delta_{12} = \frac{V_{2,L}}{V_{1,L}} \exp \left(\frac{-\lambda_{12} - \lambda_{11}}{RT} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta_{21} = \frac{V_{1,L}}{V_{2,L}} \exp \left(\frac{-\lambda_{21} - \lambda_{22}}{RT} \right) \quad (10)$$

where, $V_{1,L}$ and $V_{2,L}$ are the liquid molar volumes and $(\lambda_{12} - \lambda_{11})$ and $(\lambda_{21} - \lambda_{22})$ are the model parameters with $\lambda_{12} = \lambda_{21}$. The Wilson parameters, obtained by minimising the objective function defined by equation (1) are reported in Table 3. The two systems at 715 mm/Hg were used in data reduction.

TABLE 3—WILSON CONSTANTS $(\lambda_{12} - \lambda_{11})/R$ AND $(\lambda_{21} - \lambda_{22})/R$ FOR THE TWO SYSTEMS

System	$(\lambda_{12} - \lambda_{11})/R, K$	$(\lambda_{21} - \lambda_{22})/R, K$
n-Butylbromide-trichloroethylene	-334.89	682.72
n-Butylbromide-tetrachloroethylene	59.92	43.80

The excess Gibbs energies at 25° for the two systems were also calculated with these model parameters by using equation (11),

$$G^E = RT(X_1 \ln \gamma_1 + x_2 \ln \gamma_2) \quad (11)$$

and are presented in Table 4 and shown in Fig. 3. The G^E values are negative for the system of n-butyl bromide with trichloroethylene and positive at 0.95 mole fraction, whereas the G^E values are positive for the system n-butyl bromide with tetrachloroethylene over the entire range of composition. The maximum G^E occurs at around 0.45 and 0.5 mole fractions of n-butyl bromide in the mixture of n-butyl bromide with trichloroethylene and tetrachloroethylene respectively.

 TABLE 4—MOLE FRACTION (X_1) OF n-BUTYLBROMIDE AND EXCESS GIBBS ENERGY DATA AT 25° FOR THE MIXTURES n-BUTYLBROMIDE-TRICHLOROETHYLENE AND n-BUTYL-BROMIDE-TETRACHLOROETHYLENE

X_1	G^E J mol ⁻¹	X_1	G^E J mol ⁻¹
n-Butylbromide-trichloroethylene		n-Butylbromide-tetrachloroethylene	
0.05	-25.85	0.05	35.64
0.10	-49.40	0.10	67.88
0.15	-70.53	0.15	96.68
0.20	-89.09	0.20	121.98
0.25	-104.93	0.25	143.74
0.30	-117.88	0.30	161.88
0.35	-127.79	0.35	176.36
0.40	-134.48	0.40	187.11
0.45	-137.76	0.45	194.08
0.50	-137.47	0.50	197.19
0.55	-133.43	0.55	198.39
0.60	-125.51	0.60	191.59
0.65	-113.65	0.65	182.73
0.70	-97.88	0.70	169.72
0.75	-78.46	0.75	152.50
0.80	-56.03	0.80	130.97
0.85	-31.96	0.85	105.05
0.90	-9.13	0.90	74.64
0.95	6.33	0.95	39.66

The results of these mixtures are influenced by (i) loss of dipolar association due to the addition of less polar n-butylbromide to the more polar chlorinated ethylenes, difference in size between unlike molecules and (ii) dipole induced dipole interactions and electron-donor-acceptor complex formation. Formation of electron-donor-acceptor complexes between

Fig. 3. (O) 1-Bromobutane + 1,1,1-trichloroethylene and (●) + 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethylene at 298.15 K.

the components of these mixtures is possible due to the fact n-butyl bromide acts as an electron-donor and the chlorinated ethylene acts as an electron acceptor. The former effect results in positive values of G^E whereas the latter effect contributes to a negative value of G^E . The actual sign and magnitude of G^E of a particular system depend on the relative strength of the two effects.

References

1. F. HALA, J. PICK, V. FRIED and O. VILIM, "Vapor-Liquid Equilibrium", Pergamon, Oxford, 1967.
2. J. A. RIDDICK and W. B. BUNGER, "Organic Solvents", 3rd. ed., Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970.
3. J. TIMMERMANS, "Physicochemical Constants of Pure Organic Compounds", Elsevier, New York, 1955.
4. J. A. DEAN, "Lange's Hand Book of Chemistry", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1973.
5. C. F. SPENCER and R. P. DANNER, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1972, **17**, 236.
6. C. TSONOPOULOS, *J. AIChE*, 1974, **20**, 263.
7. T. BOVBLIK, V. FRIED and F. HALA, "The Vapor Pressures of Pure Substances", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1973.
8. R. C. REID, J. M. PRAUSNITZ and T. K. SHERWOOD, "The Properties of Gases and Liquids", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1977.
9. G. M. WILSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 127.